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Large Scale Asset Detection Within Railway Scene Point Cloud Data From Mobile Laser Scanning

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ABSTRACT To reduce greenhouse gas emissions from the transport sector, shifting to rail transport is crucial. This transition will increase the demand on existing rail infrastructure, necessitating large-scale monitoring to maintain its resilience. Point cloud data are an ideal candidate for this purpose, as they provide immediate, precise 3D geometric information independent of illumination conditions. This study investigates two object detection models, the PointPillar and the CenterPoint model, to automatically create a digital representation of the rail environment. Using a custom open dataset, these two models are evaluated to detect masts, tension rods, signals, and relay cabinets. A mean Average Precision ($mAP@0.5$) of 70.6% is achieved. A unique contribution of this study is an in-depth analysis of the locational error in terms of the x and y components of the detected positions. This analysis reveals that location accuracy is not yet sufficient for engineering applications. The analysis indicates that the largest contribution to this error originates from the random error. Additionally, this study demonstrates that transfer learning effectively reduces the labeling burden. For instance, when using 25% of the training data, the average Precision (AP) for the tension rod class improves from 9.5% without transfer learning to 70.8% with transfer learning.

INDEX TERMS Deep learning, LiDaR, mobile laser scanning, object detection, point cloud, PointPillar, railway

I. INTRODUCTION

Climate change, exacerbated by increased greenhouse gas emissions, has a serious impact on the world [1]. To mitigate these emissions, particularly from the transport sector, rail transport offers a viable solution [2]. The European Union advocates for a shift from road to rail transport as a means to significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions [3].

The anticipated rise in passenger and freight rail traffic in the near future will inevitably increase the strain on railway infrastructure. Ensuring the continued reliability, availability, maintainability and safety of the railway network in an efficient way, requires accurate and up-to-date digital representations of the railway environment. These as-is models are essential for various applications, including work planning, immersive visualizations, infrastructure health monitoring, automated inventory assessment, and predictive maintenance.

However, the automated creation of these as-is models presents significant challenges due to the complex and expansive nature of railway environments. These environments

encompass both discrete objects, such as signals, catenary arches, and relay cabinets, and continuous structures, such as overhead catenary wires and rail tracks. The diversity and number of distinct object classes, especially in countries with dense and historically rich rail networks like the Netherlands, add to the complexity.

Point clouds serve as an appropriate data source for creating these as-is models. Point clouds are collected by using a mobile laser scanner, which uses the time-of-flight of light pulses to determine the distance between sensor and object. Point clouds can be captured regardless of external illumination variations and provide immediate, precise 3D geometric information. This in contrast with image data, where the quality is influenced by external illumination conditions and where advanced photogrammetric computations are required to obtain 3D information from images.

A research area which is well established with regard to scene understanding from point cloud data is the area of autonomous driving vehicles. Typically autonomous driving

vehicles are equipped, among a plethora of other sensors, with laser scanners. The data from these laser scanners are used to detect other road users such as other vehicles, pedestrians, or cyclists. This study aims to leverage the knowledge and techniques developed for this domain and evaluate its applicability to object detection within railway environments.

Recent surveys on monitoring critical infrastructure using point cloud data indicate that most approaches do not leverage deep learning techniques. Instead, they predominantly rely on heuristic methods [4], [5]. A drawback of heuristic approaches is their dependence on numerous hand-crafted features and manually tuned parameters. To overcome this drawback, deep learning methods are able to automatically learn by providing them with ample examples. This also means that deep learning models are partially domain agnostic. For instance, this research uses models which have been developed for the road domain, but are now applied to the rail domain.

This research aims to evaluate the applicability of deep learning-based object detection in the rail domain. Additionally, it assesses the locational accuracy of deep learning-based object detection models, a factor often overlooked or ignored in other rail domain publications. The difficulty in obtaining ground truth data for object locations, due to stringent safety protocols for track access, likely contribute to this oversight. Nevertheless, accurate locational data is crucial for planning construction or deploying automated construction robots. It is estimated that the required locational accuracy for creating a digital representation of the railway environment in the Netherlands is around ± 5 cm¹. This digital representation should then be accurate enough for planning construction works without doing a manual inventory of the site.

The remainder of this article is organized as follows: First, Section II presents the related work. Thereafter the custom dataset is presented in Section III together with the pre-processing steps required to prepare the data for ingestion by the machine learning models. This is followed by the methodology in Section IV. This section describes how the models are trained and evaluation, how the effectiveness of transfer learning is evaluated, and how the locational error is analyzed. Section V presents the findings, including two approaches that yielded negative results. Finally, Section VI concludes the article with recommendations.

An earlier version of this work was previously published as part of B. Ton his PhD thesis [6]. Interested readers are encouraged to refer to this thesis to understand how the work presented here contributes to the broader goal of digitizing the rail environment.

II. RELATED WORK

This section reviews automated methods for deriving information from point cloud data to construct an as-is model of railway infrastructure. Most related works focus on specific

tasks, such as detecting tracks or components of the overhead line equipment, like catenary wires.

Zhu and Hyypä [7] utilize both Airborne Laser Scanning (ALS) and Mobile Laser Scanning (MLS) data to model the railway environment in 3D. Their non-supervised approach employs a variety of parametric models fine-tuned for each element of interest, including ground, trees, buildings, catenary arches, and overhead power lines. Notably, their method extracts building facades from MLS data and roofs from ALS data.

Pastucha [8] and Arastounia [9] present similar results, with Arastounia's work offering a higher level of detail. Both studies use parametric models to detect tracks and overhead components. Arastounia's research focuses on a 550 m stretch of Austrian railway track, achieving high accuracy metrics specific to that section. Pastucha's work evaluates around 90 km of Polish railway track, detecting over 97% of support structures.

Cheng et al. focus on creating an as-is Building Information Model (BIM) of single-track railway tunnels using Terrestrial Laser Scanner (TLS) data [10]. They heavily rely on parametric models to achieve a high-accuracy BIM in the mm-cm range.

Wolf et al. also aim at automatically detecting railway assets from point cloud data [11]. Their approach involves rendering grayscale images from point cloud slices, with pixel values representing intensity values from the original point cloud. These slices are taken perpendicular to the rail track. They present results of both object detection, based on the YOLOv3 model [12], and on semantic segmentation, based on the U-Net [13] model. An image based approach has two major benefits; the field of image processing has advanced much further than point based methods and the processing of raster data can be done much more efficient compared to point data. It should be noted that their work is still in a very premature state.

Pre-processing is a common step before modeling. In general the goal of this step is to cull the number of points, which is done to lessen the computation load. Often, this step also partitions a large scene into smaller tractable pieces.

When collecting data from the rail environment using a mobile laser scanner, the trajectory of the measurement train is typically logged. This trajectory is valuable for partitioning the large point cloud scene into smaller tractable pieces. Soilán et al. [14] describe a trajectory log based dissection method using the roll, pitch and heading information of the measurement train, with each piece set to 3 m. Their work focuses on automated rail extraction.

Lamas et al. also partition the data into smaller pieces, each with a length of 200 m and a width of 20 m, covering 90 km of track in total [15]. Each of the pieces is segmented with a high level of detail by using a heuristic-based workflow. Interestingly, Grandio et al. used the results of this work to train a fully supervised semantic segmentation model [16]. They also subjectively evaluate the generalisability of the trained model by applying it to different scenarios captured

¹Based on personal communications with Strukton Rail engineers

with various types of laser scanners. The model shows some generalisability but is heavily dependent on location and data quality.

Intriguingly, to overcome the issue of poor generalisability of models, Wang et al. have added an extra module to the network which can recognize the type of railway scene before segmentation takes place. An exploratory ablation study indicates that by utilizing this prior knowledge the mIoU is increased significantly [17].

A proper data format for exchanging information between different stakeholders is essential. This aspect is often overlooked, but Soilán et al. suggest using the open Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) to ensure interoperability [14]. IFC is also used by Ariyachandra and Brilakis [18] to model overhead line equipment.

Most related works make use of professional-grade laser scanners, such as the Riegl-VMX250. An exception is the work of Zou et al. which use a Velodyne VLP-16 laser scanner [19], the same sensor used in this study. The investment required for a professional-grade laser scanner is extremely high, which can be a bottleneck for railway contractors and railway operators. Using lower-priced laser scanners also allows for multiple scanners to be operational simultaneously, which is crucial for moving to a predictive maintenance paradigm that requires monitoring the infrastructural health over time.

In summary, most works rely on professional high-resolution laser scanners and employ semantic segmentation or parametric models to extract information from point cloud data. This work addresses this gap by using a consumer-grade laser scanner and, in contrast to the commonly used semantic segmentation task, explores the use of object detection models to detect railway assets. A major benefit of utilizing object detection models is that no ambiguous ‘background’ class needs to be defined, labeled, and learned.

III. DATA

As public point cloud datasets related to railway infrastructure were virtually nonexistent at the initiation of the project, a custom dataset has been collected. This custom dataset has been made available to the public [20]. This dataset was collected by a dedicated measurement train from Strukton Rail, the ‘Leonardo’. This measurement train is equipped with a variety of sensors, including a Velodyne VLP-16 laser scanner to capture point cloud data of the scene. Fig. 1 shows the sensor mounted center front of the train’s top. This sensor has a horizontal field of view of 360 degrees and a vertical field of view of 30 degrees, with a stated typical range accuracy of ± 3 cm. Simultaneously with the laser scanner data, the location and orientation of the measurement train are recorded with an Applanix POS LVX sensor.

The Applanix POSpac Mobile Mapping Suite was used to post-process the captured data. This post-processing step includes removing redundant data when the train was stationary and registering individual captured scenes into a larger scene.

FIGURE 1: Leonardo measurement train. Red circle indicates the position of the LiDAR sensor. Image by Strukton Rail.

As an alternative to using a mobile laser scanner, an aerial laser scanner was considered, but had several disadvantages. First, the operating costs of ALS are higher compared to MLS. Second, because the distance between scanner and scene is larger, the density of the point cloud is lower [21]. Third, the vantage point of ALS leads to a certain type of self-shadowing, which typically distorts the base of the object.

The first dataset was collected on 14 June 2021 around the Deventer-Twello region, The Netherlands. The measurement train drove four times back and forth on the same piece of track. Unfortunately, the measurement train did not turn at the end of the section, but instead drove backward. This implies that objects were not captured from both directions. Each trip of the measurement train will be referred to as a *run*. In addition to the captured point cloud, the GPS location, heading, acceleration, and odometer of the train were also logged.

An additional smaller dataset was collected around the city of Dronten, The Netherlands. This trajectory was captured on 16 November 2021 and consists of a single run.

For both areas, the EPSG:32631 coordinate reference system (CRS) was used for the captured point clouds, and Coordinated Universal Time (UTC) was used for the timestamps. The corresponding trajectory logs of the measurement train were recorded using the EPSG:4258 CRS and made use of the Central European Summer Time (CEST, UTC+02:00) and the Central European Time (CET, UTC+01:00) respectively. Fig. 2 shows the trajectory of both measurement sessions.

The average distance of a single run within the Deventer-Twello region was ≈ 6.5 km, and the length of the Dronten trajectory was ≈ 2.9 km. The key figures of the different runs are summarized in Table 1. The distance value is based on the odometer data. The table also clearly shows the correlation between speed and the number of points collected. It can be seen that run 1 had the lowest average speed of 62.4 km/h and the highest point count, while run 4 had the highest average speed of 72.1 km/h and the lowest point count. The number of points processed will be significantly reduced during the pre-processing steps. These steps are elaborated in Section III-C. To prevent repetitive labeling, all four runs were merged

(a) Deventer-Twello area.

(b) Dronten area.

FIGURE 2: Trajectories of measurement train indicated in red. Map data from OpenStreetMap.

TABLE 1: Key figures of the different runs and the Dronten test set

	Duration [s]	Distance [m]	Speed [km/h]	Points [-]
run 1	373.6	6476.6	62.4	59,607,089
run 2	325.8	6479.3	71.6	52,834,759
run 3	346.4	6476.5	67.3	55,257,052
run 4	323.4	6479.2	72.1	52,423,814
Dronten	119.8	2867.3	86.1	16,532,528

before the labeling process. To separate the individual runs again after labeling, each point has an additional attribute 'run'.

A. LABELING

Prior to labeling, the large point cloud scene is divided into sections of 250 m long using the same approach described in Section III-C1. This ensures that the sections are tractable and can be divided among multiple people performing the labeling task. As the point density of the scenes is not very high, labeling is very time-consuming, and given the explorative nature of this research, the following limited set of four object classes are defined: masts, tension rods, signals, and relay cabinets. Fig. 3 provides examples of each object class. To provide a scale perspective, an average point cloud human being with a height of 174 cm is plotted alongside the examples.

Labeling the objects within the point cloud data was done using the open-source application CloudCompare. The segment tool was used for drawing polygons around the objects of interest. In general, an unobstructed top view of the object is possible, making it easy to segment the object by drawing a polygon around it from this viewpoint. After cutting out the object, a label and a unique identifier are added as a 'Scalar Field'. Finally, all the individual pieces of the dissected scene were merged together again. The unique identifier has proven to be very useful when iterating over each of the individual objects during subsequent processing steps.

The benefit of labeling points instead of just bounding boxes is that the dataset can serve both segmentation and object detection tasks.

FIGURE 3: Samples of object classes, From top to bottom: relay cabinet, signal, tension rod, mast. Last three rows are scaled by 0.3. A human being with an average height of 174 cm is added for scale comparison.

B. KEY FIGURES

This section provides some key figures of the labeled datasets. Table 2 shows the class distribution and the mean and average number of points per object class. It can be seen that the standard deviation of number of points per object is large. This large variation can have several causes, such as the distance between sensor and object, or obstructions between sensor and object.

TABLE 2: Occurrence (Occ.) of objects and their mean (M) and standard deviation (SD) of point count per object type

	First run		Fourth run		Dronten	
	Occ.	M (SD)	Occ.	M (SD)	Occ.	M (SD)
Mast	209	992 (516)	203	892 (482)	124	983 (412)
Tension rod	29	710 (395)	30	750 (589)	24	494 (152)
Signal	20	930 (507)	22	810 (400)	9	854 (232)
Relay cabinet	35	392 (175)	34	345 (184)	2	216 (14)

The Dronten dataset shows a very low count of relay cabinets. This is attributed to presence of a sound barrier adjacent to large parts of the track. Relay cabinets usually reside on the other side of the sound barrier. This sound barrier obstructs the line-of-sight from the laser scanner, resulting in an extremely low count of relay cabinets.

C. PRE-PROCESSING

Before a model can be trained, an elaborate set of pre-processing steps is required to get the data in the right format so that it can be ingested by the model. These steps are described in the following subsections. To ensure that a local object location can be mapped to a real-world location again, it is necessary to keep track of the net transformation during each of the subsequent processing steps.

1) Partitioning

The first step in the pre-processing chain is to partition the data into equal-length pieces. After the data are collected by the measurement train, they are post-processed. During this post-processing step, the non-stationary ‘frames’ are merged to form one large point cloud. The frames collected when the measurement train is stationary are omitted. To avoid large time gaps in the timestamps of the individual points, the time is shifted to compensate for the omitted frames. Unfortunately, this time shift is not reflected in the trajectory log, implying that the timestamps of the point cloud data and the trajectory log are not in sync. This has as consequence that the partitioning of the point cloud cannot be based on temporal information but has to be based on spatial information.

The trajectory log plays an important role to define simple spatial polygons, which are then used as a cookie cutter to partition the large point cloud scene into smaller, tractable pieces. On several occasions, the measurement train drove multiple times on the same track or on an adjacent track. To distinguish individual trips, a region of interest can be defined and based on the Δt of the timestamps, making it possible to distinguish them. A large Δt means that the measurement left the region of interest and entered it again at a later time. A caveat with this approach is that the measurement train cannot change direction within the region of interest.

Based on the timestamps from the trajectory log relating to a single trip, the cookie cutter polygons are defined. This is done by first calculating the cumulative distance based on the odometer data present in the trajectory log. Together with the desired length of the pieces, it is possible to determine the locations belonging to the start and end of a piece. These locations will be referred to as p_1 and p_2 . To define a cookie cutter polygon, the slope of the line between these two points is determined. Based on this slope, it is possible to determine the slope of a line perpendicular to the line passing through the two points (p_1 and p_2). Given the desired extent of a piece and the equations of the perpendicular lines, it is possible to determine the four vertices of the polygon ($v_{x,1}, v_{x,2}$ were $x \in \{1, 2\}$). Fig. 5 clarifies the procedure; they gray shaded area indicates the current polygon. The vertices $v_{2,1}$ and $v_{2,2}$ are shared with the next polygon.

2) Alignment

The two points, p_1 and p_2 , from the previous step, which indicate the start and end position of a piece, are used for centering the scene and aligning the track along the x -axis. First, the intermediate point between p_1 and p_2 is determined and is

used to set the translational part of an affine transformation. The rotational part of the affine transformation, which aligns the scene along the x -axis, is based on the angle between the x -axis and the point p_1 .

After alignment, the point cloud is clipped in the y -direction to $[-15\text{ m}, 15\text{ m}]$. Furthermore, a voxel based sub-sampling method is applied to homogenize the point density. In this scenario, a voxel size of 5 cm was used, within each voxel the centroid of the points is calculated. The calculated centroid is used to query the nearest neighbor within the voxel, which is then returned. A grid based sub-sampling strategy is also used by Grandio et al. [16]. Density variations occur naturally due to the fact that objects close to the sensor are captured with a higher spatial density compared to objects that are further away.

3) Ground Classification

The next step in the pre-processing pipeline is to classify the scene into ground and non-ground points. This classification step serves two purposes: the first is to use the classified ground points to determine a transformation that aligns the scene to the xy -plane. The second is to reduce the amount of data being worked with by removing the ground points from the scene during training and inference. The ground classification algorithm used is based on cloth simulation [22], and the result of this classification is stored in the Classification field of the Point Data Record.

The removal of the ground plane is also done by Ariyachandra and Brilakis to reduce computation time and false positives [18].

4) Leveling

The least-squares method is used to fit a plane to the classified ground points. The normal vector of this plane is used to determine a rotation matrix that levels the scene and makes it flush with the xy -plane. Special care is taken to ensure the normal of the plane is pointing towards the positive z -direction. If this is not the case, the scene would be flipped upside down. Level normalization is an important prerequisite for the next pre-processing step, determining bounding boxes.

5) Bounding Boxes

In general, the task of object detection is to predict (oriented) bounding boxes of objects. This section describes how an oriented bounding box is obtained from a cluster of labeled points. A constraint imposed by the used models is that the top and bottom of the bounding box are flush with the xy -plane. An oriented bounding box is represented by a vector with seven elements. These elements are: the center point of the bounding box (x, y, z), the extent in all directions (ex, ey, ez) and a yaw angle (θ). The yaw angle is defined as the counter-clockwise rotation around the positive z -axis.

The processing steps to determine an oriented bounding box based on point clusters is detailed below:

- Determine convex hull of the xy -coordinates of the cluster.

FIGURE 4: Pre-processing steps.

FIGURE 5: Partitioning of the point cloud scene.

- Use a Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) of the xy -coordinates of the hull to obtain the orientation of the object.
- Rotate the cluster of points such that it aligns with the x -axis.
- Determine the extent (ex , ey , ez) of the object in x , y , z -directions.
- If $ey > ex$, swap ex and ey and add $\pi/2$ to the yaw angle.

The convex hull of the cluster of points is used to avoid point density variations altering the true orientation of the bounding box when the SVD is applied in the next step. The final step ensures that the longest side of the bounding box is always aligned with the x -axis. This is important when calculating the dimensions of the anchor boxes; otherwise, the dimensions of the anchor boxes would be distorted. Fig. 6 shows a sample scene. It shows the labeled points and the calculated bounding boxes.

Anchor box statistics

The PointPillar model requires an initial estimate of the bounding box sizes of the objects of interests. These estimates are referred to as anchor boxes. The anchor box dimensions are summarized in Table 3.

TABLE 3: Dimensions (m) of the anchor boxes of the first run per object class

	width	length	height
Mast	1.4	1.1	8.9
Tension rod	10.6	1.2	7.1
Signal	2.4	1.3	6.2
Relay cabinet	1.5	0.8	1.6

IV. METHODOLOGY

Two successful deep learning-based 3D object detection models, the PointPillar model (2019) [23] and the CenterPoint model (2021) [24], from the domain of autonomous driving will be evaluated for the task of detecting objects within the railway environment. The PointPillar and CenterPoint object detection models are chosen for this application because they offer good performance in terms of average precision and have a low inference time, making them suitable for practical applications [25]. The CenterPoint model supports both a pillar-based discretization and a voxel-based discretisation of the scene. To ensure a fair comparison between both models, the pillar-based discretization is used.

Both models utilize the SECOND backbone [26], which is an improved version of the VoxelNet backbone [27]. The main difference between the two models is the type of head. The CenterPoint model uses a two-stage approach: first, the center of the object is located (hence the name); second, a regression head is used to predict the bounding box and orientation. This implies that no prior information about the box size in the form of anchor boxes is required. The PointPillar model, on the other hand, uses a Single Shot Detector (SSD) to estimate bounding boxes in the 2D Bird's Eye View (BEV). The 3D bounding box height, and elevation are additional regression targets. The original CenterPoint model includes velocity as a regression output; however, for this study, the velocity regression head has been removed completely from the model.

The grid size used by the original CenterPoint model is $(0.2 \times 0.2 \text{ m})$ or $(0.32 \times 0.32 \text{ m})$, depending on the dataset being evaluated. The grid size used by the original PointPillar mode is $(0.16 \times 0.16 \text{ m})$. In an ablation study, the authors of

FIGURE 6: Sample scene. Red: masts, blue: tension rods, magenta: signals, yellow: relay cabinets, and black: background. Labeled points and calculated bounding boxes are visible. Best viewed in color.

the PointPillar model show that the performance diminishes as the grid size increases. Therefore, for this study, a grid size of $\approx (0.1 \times 0.1 \text{ m})$ has been used. This grid size has been chosen as a good balance between locational accuracy and memory consumption of the model. The resulting grid size was 736×304 .

A. EVALUATION METHOD

All possible permutations for training, validation and testing are evaluated on the four runs of the Deventer-Twello dataset. This means that a total of $4! = 24$ experiments are conducted. The model that performs best on the validation set is used for testing. The mean average precision (mAP) specified at an Intersection over Union (IoU) threshold of 0.5 and 0.75 are used as final metric. The results of all permutations are averaged and presented with the standard deviation.

The software framework used for evaluating the model is non-deterministic. Hence, to reduce the variability of the validation and test results, the validation and testing datasets are iterated ten times when determining the AP values.

As there is no standardized definition of calculating the mAP, the details of the calculation are provided here. The metric used in this work could be considered a vanilla type of mAP. When determining the precision and recall values, the confidence threshold is varied. In our work all encountered prediction certainty scores are used as confidence threshold values. The IoU values are volume-based.

In addition to the overall average precision scores, the impact of point count for the mast class is also evaluated. This class was chosen as it is the most common class in the dataset. To evaluate the impact, the masts have been divided into four quantiles based on point count. For each quantile the recall

curve is determined; the precision-recall is not considered, as it would be impossible to determine to which quantile a *False Positive* will contribute. For each confidence threshold, the recall (Equation 1) is calculated, where *TP* refers to the number of *True Positives* and *FN* refers to the number of *False Negatives*. The IoU threshold is set to 0.5.

$$\text{Recall} = \frac{TP}{TP + FN} \quad (1)$$

The final metric reported will be the Area Under Recall Curve (AUREC).

B. TRANSFER LEARNING

Labeling data is an expensive endeavor. Therefore, it is valuable to know how much effort is required to get good results from an unseen, new piece of track. Transfer learning is a successful technique to make use of an existing trained model and fine-tune it for new data [28], [29].

The Dronten dataset is used to get insights into how much new training is required to obtain good results. The dataset is manually split into four distinct subsets, ensuring that the distribution of classes is roughly equal among these subsets.

The amount of new training data are varied, by taking 0%, 25%, 50%, and 75% of the Dronten dataset. The remaining data are used for testing. As there are very few examples of relay cabinets present in this dataset, this class is omitted for this experiment. As the dataset is too small to also have a proper validation set, the number of training epochs is fixed to 600. The learning rate is set to 1×10^{-4} . The reported metric will be the mAP of the test set based on the weights of epoch 600.

The number of possible permutations of training and testing sets for the case of 25% and 75% is four. For the case of 50% training data, the number of permutations is twelve. All permutations are trained and evaluated, and the average mAP is reported. An initial single model is trained on the Deventer-Twello dataset with the relay cabinet class ignored. This initial model is then fine-tuned using varying amount of training data from the Dronten dataset.

C. LOCALATIONAL ERROR

The locational error between the ground truth location and the location predicted by the machine learning models can be decomposed into two components: the random error and the systematic error [30]. We will adhere to the terminology set out by the ISO 5725-1 standard [31]. This standard introduces the concept of trueness, which captures the systematic error, and precision, which captures the random error. Both error components combined constitute the accuracy. The errors are analyzed for the masts and cabinets together, along with an overall analysis. The other two asset classes, tension rods and signals, are not considered as it is not possible to define a precise origin for these two classes. For instance, in our case, the tension rods have been labeled together with their concrete foundation, while the reference data only labeled the rods themselves. A similar case holds for the signals; in our case, signals have been labeled together with the attached staircase, while the reference data did not.

Evaluation of the locational accuracy of the assets detected by the machine learning model requires accurate ground truth data. Often, these data are not available as it requires considerable resources to obtain them, especially for longer stretches of track. As an alternative, the Dutch railway manager ProRail provides the absolute location of a large number of railway assets situated in the Netherlands. The locations of selected assets are publicly made available using a Web Feature Service (WFS)² which can be queried. It is not known how these locations are obtained, but it is most likely done using photogrammetry, and the expected accuracy of these locations is unknown. Hence, the first step will be to evaluate the locational accuracy of the data provided by ProRail.

To do so, a geodetic survey was carried out using a Leica GS18 GNSS RTK rover during the night of 28–29 January 2024. To get foot access to the tracks a special permit was required and the mandated personal protective equipment was used. The data sheet of this rover lists a mean horizontal accuracy of 7 mm and a mean vertical accuracy of 25 mm. Seventy-four objects (4 signals, 12 catenary rods and 58 masts) were manually surveyed and compared to the dataset provided by ProRail. We would like to emphasize that the rover does not collect point cloud data, but instead a single accurate location for each object is measured manually. The masts were all steel H-profile style masts, the center of the H on the ground plate has been used as measurement point. Based on mast locations, it was concluded that all objects

surveyed fall within a locational accuracy of 10 centimeters horizontal (μ 8.7 cm, σ 4.5 cm with a maximum error of 19.6 cm). Therefore, we consider the locations provided by ProRail a valid proxy source for the ground truth.

The ProRail data are then used to evaluate the locational accuracy of the detected objects. For an object to be included in the evaluation, it must be within 3 meters of the location specified by ProRail. In the case of relay cabinets, which are usually clustered and reside within 3 meters of each other, a manual inspection was conducted to correctly match object detections to the ProRail-specified locations. Additionally, the detected object must have the correct label; otherwise, the detection was excluded. To get meaningful results when comparing locations of objects, both datasets must use the same origin. For the catenary masts and cabinets, the horizontal position of the origin is set to the center of these objects. The ProRail data do not include the vertical position (z -component) or the orientation of objects. Therefore, the decision was made to include only the horizontal components in the evaluation of the locational accuracy.

The locational error is analyzed for the mast and cabinet asset classes. For each asset class, there are n_{gt} ground truth locations, and for each ground truth location, there are $n_{d,i}$ detections from the models. In total, for a certain asset class, there will be n_d detections. Let p_i be a vector denoting a specific ground truth location, where i is an index over the number of ground truth locations for this asset class. Let $\tilde{p}_{i,j}$ be another vector, specifying a certain detection corresponding to a ground truth location i , and j is an index over the number of detections for this ground truth location.

1) Trueness

To determine the trueness, the systematic error vector δ can be determined based on the difference between the ground truth locations and the detections from the machine learning models. Equation 2 shows how this systematic error vector is formally defined.

$$\delta = \frac{1}{n_d} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{gt}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{d,i}} \tilde{p}_{i,j} - p_i \quad (2)$$

The trueness for an asset class is defined as the norm of the systematic error vector, that is $\|\delta\|$.

2) Precision

The precision of the detections will be represented by the standard deviation of the measurements. The standard deviation will be represented by a vector σ , consisting of the elements σ_x and σ_y . As an example, the calculations for determining the standard deviation σ_x are provided, σ_y is derived in the same way. To determine the standard deviation σ_x of the detections corresponding to a ground truth location p_i , first the arithmetic mean $\tilde{\mu}_i$ of the detections $\tilde{p}_{i,j}$ is determined. Thereafter, Equation 3 shows how this mean value is used to determine the precision.

²<https://mapservices.prorail.nl>

$$\sigma_x = \frac{1}{n_{gr}} \sum_{i=1}^{n_{gr}} \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{j=1}^{n_{d,i}} (\tilde{p}_{i,j_x} - \tilde{\mu}_{i_x})^2}{n_{d,i}}} \quad (3)$$

The overall precision is defined as $\|\sigma\|$.

3) Accuracy

The overall locational accuracy for a certain asset class will be measured using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) vector. This metric encompasses both trueness and precision. The RMSE vector for a single ground truth location i is composed of the individual m_{i_x} and m_{i_y} components. Equation 4 shows how the m_{i_x} component is calculated. The other component is calculated in similar fashion.

$$m_{i_x} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n_{d,i}} \sum_{j=1}^{n_{d,i}} (\tilde{p}_{i,j_x} - p_{i_x})^2} \quad (4)$$

Finally, the RMSE can be calculated using Equation 5.

$$RMSE_i = \sqrt{m_{i_x}^2 + m_{i_y}^2} \quad (5)$$

The reported RMSE for a certain asset class will be the average of all RMSE values belonging to this asset class.

D. TRAINING SETUP

Due to memory consumption of the model during training, a batch size of one is used. Initially the model had difficulty converging; this is why for training a Stochastic Gradient Descent (SGD) optimizer is used instead of the default Adam optimizer. SGD provides a better generalization, with the penalty of having a slower training time [32]. A total of 3000 epochs are trained, with an initial learning rate of 1×10^{-3} , which is reduced to 1×10^{-4} after 1500 epochs. Every 50 epochs, the model is validated, and the weights corresponding to the highest mAP of the validation set are retained. These model weights are later used for testing.

The models are trained on a desktop computer with 64 GB of RAM, an AMD Ryzen Threadripper 2950X CPU, and an NVIDIA TITAN V GPU with 12 GB of memory.

V. RESULTS

First, the object detection results are presented in terms of average precision. Additionally, the impact of point density on the recall rate of the catenary masts is presented. Thereafter, the effectiveness of transfer learning is analyzed. Because accurate locational information is essential when creating ‘assis’ models, an in depth analysis of the locational error is provided. Finally, two rejected hypotheses are presented for completeness.

A. OBJECT DETECTION

The aggregated object detection results are presented in Table 4. The table shows the average precision results averaged across the different experiments, along with the standard deviation.

TABLE 4: Mean AP@0.5 and AP@0.75 results for all combinations of training, validation, and testing. Standard deviation in brackets

Asset	IoU ≥ 0.5		IoU ≥ 0.75	
	PointPillar	CenterPoint	PointPillar	CenterPoint
Mast	78.5 (11.1)	72.8 (8.5)	16.3 (9.6)	7.5 (4.1)
Tension rod	71.7 (11.9)	64.3 (14.1)	12.6 (8.7)	9.7 (4.8)
Signal	83.5 (7.0)	82.1 (7.0)	16.3 (11.3)	14.0 (6.5)
Relay cabinet	48.6 (11.5)	36.3 (13.1)	2.4 (2.5)	0.5 (1.2)
<i>mAP</i>	70.6 (8.0)	63.9 (6.8)	14.6 (15.1)	10.3 (11.8)

From the table, it can be seen that the performance quickly degrades when an IoU threshold of 0.75 is used. This is already an indication of poor locational accuracy, as the IoU directly depends on how well bounding boxes overlap. An in-depth analysis of the locational accuracy is provided in Section IV-C. The table also shows that the PointPillar model has the best performance for all classes, albeit with a slightly higher standard deviation.

The results of determining the impact of point count on the recall rate are provided in Table 5. The first and last quantile show the largest spread in point count. The samples column specifies the number of samples falling within the listed interval.

TABLE 5: Area Under Recall Curve (AUREC) for each quantile for the masts using an IoU threshold of 0.5

Quantile	Interval	Samples	AUREC
1	[159, 629)	212	58.9 (11.2)
2	[629, 783)	210	67.5 (11.3)
3	[783, 1076)	214	62.8 (9.3)
4	[1076, 4486]	212	63.8 (7.4)

Surprisingly, the data does not show a positive correlation between point count and the AUREC. This was expected, as a higher point count would also imply more information for the machine learning model to learn from.

B. TRANSFER LEARNING

The results of the transfer learning experiments are presented in Table 6. It should be noted that the results mentioned for the signal class are very imprecise, as the number of signals per split was very limited (1,2,2,4).

TABLE 6: With and without Transfer Learning (TL) for varying amounts of training data. AP@IoU=0.5

	No TL				With TL			
	0%	25%	50%	75%	0%	25%	50%	75%
Mast	–	70.3	84.3	82.5	57.0	86.3	90.0	91.5
Tension rod	–	9.5	42.4	60.0	21.0	70.8	71.8	74.3
Signal	–	8.5	6.8	12.5	6.0	6.8	19.3	12.5

The table shows a clear benefit when using transfer learning. For instance, when using 25% of the training data, the AP for the tension rod class jumps from 9.5% to 70.8%.

C. LOCATIONAL ERROR

The object detection experiments led to a combined total of 11,761 detections for the mast and relay cabinet class. From these detections, 1,957 detections were excluded from the test based on the criteria stipulated in Section IV-C, resulting in 9,804 usable detections available for analysis. A detailed breakdown of the usable detections for the locational error analysis is provided in Table 7.

TABLE 7: Breakdown of usable detections from both models

Object	PointPillar	CenterPoint
Mast	4389	4327
Relay cabinet	551	537

First, the locational trueness and precision of the objects detected by the machine learning model are presented. Secondly, the locational accuracy values are presented based on the RMSE.

1) Trueness

The results of the trueness analysis can be found in Table 8. The various experiments of both the PointPillar and the CenterPoint models showed similar results for each object.

TABLE 8: Locational trueness analysis (centimeters)

Object	PointPillar			CenterPoint		
	δ_x	δ_y	$\ \delta\ $	δ_x	δ_y	$\ \delta\ $
Mast	3.41	7.56	8.30	3.08	7.30	7.92
Relay cabinet	4.73	9.59	10.69	4.83	10.86	11.88
<i>Overall</i>	3.56	7.79	8.56	3.27	7.70	8.36

2) Precision

The results of locational precision can be found in Table 9. Again, the various experiments of both the PointPillar and the CenterPoint models showed similar results for each object. The precision values fall almost completely within the accuracy of the fixed marks used for comparison.

TABLE 9: Locational precision analysis (centimeters)

Object	PointPillar			CenterPoint		
	σ_x	σ_y	$\ \sigma\ $	σ_x	σ_y	$\ \sigma\ $
Mast	10.35	11.97	15.83	9.49	10.07	13.83
Relay cabinet	17.28	12.08	21.09	24.57	11.85	27.28
<i>Overall</i>	11.33	11.98	16.49	12.14	10.28	15.90

3) Accuracy

The results of locational accuracy can be found in Table 10.

In general, the overall locational accuracy is not yet within what is required for (automated) engineering applications. From the results, it can be seen that the random error (precision) has the largest contribution to the overall accuracy. Since it is a random error, it should be possible to mitigate

TABLE 10: Locational accuracy analysis (centimeters)

Object	PointPillar			CenterPoint		
	m_x	m_y	RMSE	m_x	m_y	RMSE
Mast	15.06	20.80	25.68	14.85	19.53	24.52
Relay cabinet	19.35	18.11	26.50	26.80	19.25	32.99
<i>Overall</i>	15.50	20.52	25.78	16.60	19.50	25.61

this by averaging multiple measurements. There are several possible factors influencing the accuracy, which have been summarized below.

- Grid size; the finer the grid, the more accurate a location can be determined.
- Annotation noise; errors can be attributed to intra-annotator precision, and data interpretation differences.
- Net transform; which is used to map from a local coordinate system back to the global coordinate reference system. Any errors in keeping track of the net transform will be reflected in the locational accuracy.
- Conversions; conversions between different coordinate reference systems.
- GPS accuracy; the GPS system of the measurement train and the post-processing steps involved will also impact the locational accuracy.
- Ground truth accuracy; the location of the detected objects are compared to some (proxy) ground truth reference. In practice, this ground truth will also have a certain accuracy.
- Sensor; the sensor also has factors which impact the locational accuracy such as resolution, noise, and capturing artifacts.

D. REJECTED HYPOTHESES

For the sake of completeness and to combat positive-results bias, this section details two approaches that were attempted but were not fruitful in the long run. The first approach relates to an alternative and a more recent object detection algorithm, and the second approach relates to semantic segmentation of point cloud data.

1) DSVT Model

The Dynamic Sparse Voxel Transformer (DSVT) is a more recent model [33] which was published in 2023, compared to the PointPillar model which was published in 2019. On paper, this model has better results compared to the PointPillar model, with an mAP of 79.5 versus an mAP of 69.0 for the Waymo dataset [34]. The hypothesis was that if this newer model has a higher mAP on the benchmark dataset, it should also perform better on our own data. Despite a grid search for optimal hyper-parameters, it was not possible to surpass the 0.5 mAP threshold for our custom rail scene dataset. The reason for this is not known; it could be related to the implementation of the model or still a poor choice of hyper-parameters.

2) Semantic Segmentation

During experimentation, it was realized that object detection-based localization of railway assets does not provide the required locational accuracy. This is caused by the fact that most object detection models are grid-based, labeling inaccuracies exist, and the predicted bounding boxes are not tight. To completely overcome the localization accuracy dependency on grid size, an attempt was made to use a segmentation-based model. Based on the fact that semantic segmentation provides a label per point and is not grid-based, the hypothesis was that with some post-processing, the location accuracy of objects should be significantly higher. An additional envisioned benefit of segmentation based models is that 'continuous' objects such as tracks and wires can be classified with the same model.

To test this hypothesis in practice, an initial experiment was conducted with the PointNet++ model to semantically segment the railway scene. The task was to segment the point cloud into the following individual classes: background, mast, signal, tension rod and cabinet. It was quickly realized that this approach would not be fruitful, as the background class accounts for 98% of the dataset.

VI. CONCLUSION

This study has examined large-scale object detection based on point cloud data for the railway environment. These object detections are required to create 'as-is' models, which can then be used for a wide range of applications. Two deep learning models from the domain of autonomous vehicles have been evaluated for object detection from point cloud data. An overall mAP@0.5 of 70.6% has been achieved for our custom dataset using the PointPillar model. This custom dataset has been collected for this study due to the lack of large public (benchmark) datasets for the rail domain.

A limitation of this study, caused by the small custom dataset, is that the main results only present how well the models generalize to repeated measurements. Based on an additional smaller custom dataset, it can be concluded that the models do not generalize well to new railway environments. To overcome this, this research has shown that transfer learning is a viable approach to quickly adapt existing models to new railway scenarios. As an example, when using 25% of the new training data the AP for the tension rod class jumps from 9.5% (no transfer learning) to 70.8% (with transfer learning).

Furthermore, this study has conducted an in-depth analysis of the locational error, which is defined as the difference between the ground truth location and the location of objects estimated by the model. Based on this analysis, it is concluded that the estimated required ± 5 cm level of accuracy can not be achieved yet. This analysis decomposed the accuracy into a systematic component and a random component. The random error had the largest contribution to the overall error. Both models showed similar results for the locational error.

A. RECOMMENDATIONS

For tasks related to autonomous driving, there are many large annotated public point cloud datasets available [35]. For tasks related to the railway environment, there were no large public dataset available at the time this study was initiated. Recently, in 2023/2024, some public datasets related to the rail domain have been published [36]–[38]. It is recommended to utilize these new datasets and evaluated the performance. As these datasets are from very diverse geographic regions, they automatically provide a large variation of object types.

An alternative cost-effective approach to obtaining labeled data is to use synthetic data. For instance, the work of Neri and Battisti create a full virtual environment of the railway and use a virtual laser scanner to generate data [39]. To create a more realistic synthesized scene, the work of Uggla and Horemuz use a hybrid approach where real data and purely synthetic data are combined to create artificial point clouds of railroad level crossings [40].

Obtaining sufficient high-quality annotations for point cloud data is an expensive task. To alleviate this problem, self-supervised pre-training of the model can be used. A pre-trained model requires less labeled data to achieve similar performances compared to models which are trained from scratch with large amounts of labeled data. A common method of self-supervised learning is contrastive learning, which has been used by Zhang et al. on point cloud data with good results [41]. It is recommended to also evaluate this approach for the rail domain.

In the case of autonomous vehicles, the deep-learning model consumes frames one-by-one from the laser scanner. A frame consists of all the points collected during a single rotation of the laser scanner. An advantage of this frame data is that it is always relative to the position of the sensor. This is very useful for autonomous driving because we want to know the location of objects such as other cars, cyclists, and pedestrians relative to the car. Unfortunately, in our case, it was not possible to obtain the raw frame-by-frame point cloud data. Hence, extensive pre-processing operations were required to split large point clouds into tractable pieces and normalize it so that the data can be ingested by the models. Since the majority of object detection models are developed with autonomous driving in mind, most of these models consume a single frame as input. It would be worthwhile to research whether better results for the railway environment can be achieved by using frame-by-frame data as input source.

Object detection models aimed at the domain of autonomous vehicles prioritize inference speed and collision avoidance over positional accuracy. To address this problem, two approaches are possible. First, an alternative paradigm of object detection models can be explored. Second, additional post-processing steps can be added to the pipeline to increase the locational accuracy.

Practitioners aiming to utilize mobile laser scanners must also consider the limitations of these devices. One significant limitation is the issue of occlusions. For instance, as mentioned in Section III-B, occlusions can hinder the accu-

rate capture of railway assets. In this case, sound barriers obstructed the laser scanner's view, resulting in many relay cabinets not being captured. To address this challenge, it is advisable to supplement the data with alternative sources, such as aerial images, which can provide a different perspective of the scene.

Currently, a vanilla-style mAP metric is used to evaluate the performance of the models. Recently, the nuScenes detection score [42] (NDS) has gained traction. This metric normalizes for the fact that objects closer to the sensor are captured with a higher density compared to objects further away from the sensor. The metric also accounts for the size of objects. It is advised to also mention this metric in future work.

The quantiles that were defined to analyze the impact of point density on the recall rate of catenary masts were based on equal group size. Alternative ways to define these quantiles, and the impact thereof, can be explored.

The current work was not able to determine the orientational accuracy of the detected objects, as the orientation of objects were not recorded in the ground truth data. It is recommended to take into account existing limitations of various models when estimating orientations. For instance, Yin et al. show a clear difference in rotational accuracy when anchor-based and center-based models are compared [24].

Furthermore, the current work does not add overlap when partitioning the data into tractable pieces. It is expected that adding overlap will lead to a better utilization of the labeled data, circumventing the problem of objects being split when they reside on the boundaries of the cut.

SOFTWARE

Point Data Abstraction Library (2.5.2), CloudCompare (2.12.4), MMDetection3D (1.1)

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REFERENCES

- [1] D. R. Easterling, G. A. Meehl, C. Parmesan, S. A. Changnon, T. R. Karl, and L. O. Mearns, "Climate extremes: Observations, modeling, and impacts," *Science*, vol. 289, pp. 2068–2074, Sep. 2000.
- [2] B. A. Gyamfi, F. V. Bekun, D. Balsalobre-Lorente, S. T. Onifade, and A. B. Ampomah, "Beyond the environmental Kuznets curve: Do combined impacts of air transport and rail transport matter for environmental sustainability amidst energy use in E7 economies?" *Environment, Development and Sustainability*, vol. 24, pp. 11 852–11 870, Oct. 2022.
- [3] E. E. Agency, B. van Zeebroeck, I. Mayeres, and S. Boschmans, "Transport and environment report 2020 – Train or plane?" 2021.
- [4] Z. Sharifisoraki, A. Dey, R. Selzler, M. Amini, J. R. Green, S. Rajan, and F. A. Kwamena, "Monitoring critical infrastructure using 3D LiDAR point clouds," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 314–336, 2023.
- [5] B. Dekker, B. Ton, J. Meijer, N. Bouali, J. Linssen, and F. Ahmed, "Point cloud analysis of railway infrastructure: A systematic literature review," *IEEE Access*, vol. 11, pp. 134 355–134 373, 2023.
- [6] B. Ton, "Point taken: Translating the physical rail domain to cyber space using point clouds from mobile laser scanning," Ph.D. dissertation, University of Twente, 2024.
- [7] L. Zhu and J. Hyypä, "The use of airborne and mobile laser scanning for modeling railway environments in 3D," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 6, pp. 3075–3100, 2014.
- [8] E. Pastucha, "Catenary system detection, localization and classification using mobile scanning data," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 8, Sep. 2016.
- [9] M. Arastounia, "Automated recognition of railroad infrastructure in rural areas from LiDAR data," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 7, pp. 14 916–14 938, Nov. 2015.
- [10] Y. J. Cheng, W. G. Qiu, and D. Y. Duan, "Automatic creation of as-is building information model from single-track railway tunnel point clouds," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 106, Oct. 2019.
- [11] J. Wolf, R. Richter, and J. Döllner, "Asset detection in railroad environments using deep learning-based scanline analysis," in *16th International Joint Conference on Computer Vision, Imaging and Computer Graphics Theory and Applications (VISIGRAPP)*, vol. 4. SciTePress, 2021, pp. 465–470.
- [12] J. Redmon and A. Farhadi, "YOLOv3: An incremental improvement," 2018.
- [13] O. Ronneberger, P. Fischer, and T. Brox, "U-Net: Convolutional networks for biomedical image segmentation," in *Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention (MICCAI)*, ser. LNCS, vol. 9351. Springer, Oct. 2015, pp. 234–241.
- [14] M. Soilán, A. Nóvoa, A. Sánchez-Rodríguez, A. Justo, and B. Riveiro, "Fully automated methodology for the delineation of railway lanes and the generation of IFC alignment models using 3D point cloud data," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 126, Jun. 2021.
- [15] D. Lamas, M. Soilán, J. Grandío, and B. Riveiro, "Automatic point cloud semantic segmentation of complex railway environments," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 13, Jun. 2021.
- [16] J. Grandío, B. Riveiro, M. Soilán, and P. Arias, "Point cloud semantic segmentation of complex railway environments using deep learning," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 141, Sep. 2022.
- [17] Z. Wang, Y. Geng, L. Jia, Y. Qin, Y. Chai, L. Tong, and K. Liu, "Self-attentive local aggregation learning with prototype guided regularization for point cloud semantic segmentation of high-speed railways," *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2023.
- [18] M. R. M. F. Ariyachandra and I. Brilakis, "Digital twinning of railway overhead line equipment from airborne LiDAR data," in *37th International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC)*, H. Osumi, H. Furuya, and K. Tateyama, Eds. International Association for Automation and Robotics in Construction (IAARC), Oct. 2020, pp. 1270–1277.
- [19] R. Zou, X. Fan, C. Qian, W. Ye, P. Zhao, J. Tang, and H. Liu, "An efficient and accurate method for different configurations railway extraction based on mobile laser scanning," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 11, Dec. 2019.
- [20] B. Ton and Strukton Rail, "[dataset] annotated mobile laser scans of the dutch railway environment," 2023.
- [21] A. Kukko, H. Kaartinen, J. Hyypä, and Y. Chen, "Multiplatform mobile laser scanning: Usability and performance," *Sensors*, vol. 12, no. 9, pp. 11 712–11 733, 2012.
- [22] W. Zhang, J. Qi, P. Wan, H. Wang, D. Xie, X. Wang, and G. Yan, "An easy-to-use airborne LiDAR data filtering method based on cloth simulation," *Remote Sensing*, vol. 8, Jun. 2016.
- [23] A. H. Lang, S. Vora, H. Caesar, L. Zhou, J. Yang, and O. Beijbom, "Point-Pillars: Fast encoders for object detection from point clouds," in *IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*, 2019, pp. 12 689–12 697.
- [24] T. Yin, X. Zhou, and P. Krähnenbühl, "Center-based 3D object detection and tracking," in *IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE Computer Society, 2021, pp. 11 779–11 788.
- [25] Y. Guo, H. Wang, Q. Hu, H. Liu, L. Liu, and M. Bennamoun, "Deep learning for 3D point clouds: A survey," *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, vol. 43, pp. 4338–4364, Dec. 2021.
- [26] Y. Yan, Y. Mao, and B. Li, "Second: Sparsely embedded convolutional detection," *Sensors (Switzerland)*, vol. 18, Oct. 2018.
- [27] Y. Zhou and O. Tuzel, "VoxelNet: End-to-end learning for point cloud based 3D object detection," in *IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE, Jun. 2018, pp. 4490–4499.
- [28] A. S. Razavian, H. Azizpour, J. Sullivan, and S. Carlsson, "CNN features off-the-shelf: An astounding baseline for recognition," in *IEEE/CVF Con-*

- ference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR). IEEE, Jun. 2014, pp. 512–519.
- [29] N. Tajbakhsh, J. Y. Shin, S. R. Gurudu, R. T. Hurst, C. B. Kendall, M. B. Gotway, and J. Liang, “Convolutional neural networks for medical image analysis: Full training or fine tuning?” *IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging*, vol. 35, pp. 1299–1312, May 2016.
- [30] P. Regtien, F. van der Heijden, M. Korsten, and W. Olthuis, *Measurement Science for Engineers*. Butterworth-Heinemann, 2004.
- [31] ISO 5725-1, “Accuracy (trueness and precision) of measurement methods and results,” International Organization for Standardization, Standard, 2023.
- [32] P. Zhou, J. Feng, C. Ma, C. Xiong, and S. Hoi, “Towards theoretically understanding why SGD generalizes better than Adam in deep learning,” in *34th International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems (NIPS)*. Curran Associates Inc., 2020, pp. 27 290–27 304.
- [33] H. Wang, C. Shi, S. Shi, M. Lei, S. Wang, D. He, B. Schiele, and L. Wang, “DSVT: Dynamic sparse voxel transformer with rotated sets,” in *IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE, Jun. 2023, pp. 13 520–13 529.
- [34] P. Sun, H. Kretzschmar, X. Dotiwalla, A. Chouard, V. Patnaik, P. Tsui, J. Guo, Y. Zhou, Y. Chai, B. Caine, V. Vasudevan, W. Han, J. Ngiam, H. Zhao, A. Timofeev, S. Ettinger, M. Krivokon, A. Gao, A. Joshi, Y. Zhang, J. Shlens, Z. Chen, and D. Anguelov, “Scalability in perception for autonomous driving: Waymo open dataset,” in *IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE, Jun. 2020, pp. 2443–2451.
- [35] H. Yin and C. Berger, “When to use what data set for your self-driving car algorithm: An overview of publicly available driving datasets,” in *20th International Conference on Intelligent Transportation Systems (ITSC)*. IEEE, Oct. 2017.
- [36] A. Kharroubi, Z. Ballouch, R. Hajji, A. Yarroudh, and R. Billen, “Multi-context point cloud dataset and machine learning for railway semantic segmentation,” *Infrastructures*, vol. 9, Apr. 2024.
- [37] R. Tilly, P. Neumaier, K. Schwalbe, P. Klasek, R. Tagiew, P. Denzler, T. Klockau, M. Boekhoff, and M. Köppel, “Open sensor data for rail 2023,” 2023.
- [38] B. Qiu, Y. Zhou, L. Dai, B. Wang, J. Li, Z. Dong, C. Wen, Z. Ma, and B. Yang, “WHU-Railway3D: A diverse dataset and benchmark for railway point cloud semantic segmentation,” *IEEE Transactions on Intelligent Transportation Systems*, 2024.
- [39] M. Neri and F. Battisti, “3D object detection on synthetic point clouds for railway applications,” in *10th European Workshop on Visual Information Processing (EUVIP)*. IEEE, Sep. 2022.
- [40] G. Uggla and M. Horemuz, “Towards synthesized training data for semantic segmentation of mobile laser scanning point clouds: Generating level crossings from real and synthetic point cloud samples,” *Automation in Construction*, vol. 130, Oct. 2021.
- [41] Z. Zhang, R. Girdhar, A. Joulin, and I. Misra, “Self-supervised pretraining of 3D features on any point-cloud,” in *IEEE/CVF International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV)*. IEEE, Oct. 2021, pp. 10 232–10 243.
- [42] H. Caesar, V. Bankiti, A. H. Lang, S. Vora, V. E. Liong, Q. Xu, A. Krishnan, Y. Pan, G. Baldan, and O. Beijbom, “nuScenes: A multimodal dataset for autonomous driving,” in *IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR)*. IEEE, Jun. 2020, pp. 11 618–11 628.

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